

METHODS OF TEACHING PHONETICS IN OTHER LANGUAGE GROUPS

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Abstract. *Phonetics makes connections between other fields of linguistics, such as literature and physiology. Also, this article provides recommendations for using the phonetics department in the educational process, which includes modern teaching methods for different language groups. In addition, in this article, the structure of phonetics, properties of sounds, sections of phonetics are given.*

Keywords: *phonetics, linguistic level, language level, explosive-sliding sound.*

МЕТОДИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ ФОНЕТИКЕ В ДРУГИЕ ЯЗЫКОВЫЕ ГРУППЫ

Аннотация. *Фонетика устанавливает связи между другими областями языкознания, такими как литература и физиология. Также в данной статье даны рекомендации по использованию в учебном процессе кафедры фонетики, включающей в себя современные методики обучения для разных языковых групп. Кроме того, в этой статье приведены структура фонетики, свойства звуков, разделы фонетики.*

Ключевые слова: *фонетика, языковой уровень, языковой уровень, взрывно-скользящий звук.*

Both the lowest level of language and the branch of linguistics that studies it are referred to as phonetics. In addition to the functional component of the source of learning, phonetics (Greek *phonetikos*, meaning "sound, sound") distinguishes from other areas of linguistics in the pronouncing apparatus that produces speech sounds as well as their acoustic characteristics and perception by speakers. Phonetics makes the connections between other linguistics areas and fields like literature, physiology, physics, and psychology more clear.

Phonetics stands out among the linguistic levels as the smallest constituent and the unit that serves as the structural foundation for the units of other levels. The units of speech used by humans to communicate are sounds or sound systems, which are perceived by the body's sensory organs. A complicated speech unit with three components is how speech sounds present themselves. As follows:

- a) a product of the central nervous system controlled by the organs of pronunciation (physiological);
- b) has an acoustic nature (physical, acoustic aspect) like any sound in nature;
- c) means of communication, information (functional, social, linguistic) of people.

Speech sound's functional component is the true and most significant aspect. The three aforementioned components of linguistics research are not uniformly studied either collectively or separately. Some experts contend that the physiology of speech sound is a matter of biology, the acoustics of speech sound is a matter of physics, and linguists should only look at the functional side, while others contend that all three aspects are interrelated and should be studied as a whole. This argument is based on belief. Phonetics and phonology, two fields of linguistics, were split as a result of the conflict between these viewpoints. As a result, phonology became the

study of the linguistic variety while phonetics became the study of the speech variant (specificity) (generality).

General phonetics is the study of the general acoustic characteristics of sound as well as the general conditions for the production of speech sounds based on the capabilities of the human pronunciation apparatus (e.g., differentiation of lip, tongue, and throat consonants instead of formation, explosive according to the method of formation, detection of sliding, explosive-sliding sound properties, etc.). Additionally, it deals with the internal articulatory and auditory classification of speech sounds. General phonetics examines the phonetic structure of parts, including the issues of stress and synharmonism, as well as the laws of sound aggregation, the nature of the effect of one sound on another (different manifestations of accommodation and assimilation), the nature of the joint, the law of accumulation of sound in the joint, and the conditions of division. The methods used for intonation (volume, strength (intensity), length, speed (tempo), pause, and timbre are among the topics covered by general phonetics.

The terms "sound" and "phoneme" are distinct in linguistics. This contrast illustrates a crucial link between specificity and generalization in science. The sensory organs sense the features when anything is being observed directly. Evaluating one comparing one property to another indicates how similar and unlike these properties are. Each characteristic is put into a certain commonality—a class—based on similarities. Similar to this, when speaking, a person directly hears noises. The smallest unit of language, a phoneme, is responsible for forming and identifying units that are superior to itself in a language, such as words, word forms, and morphemes. takes into consideration those who identify distinct sounds from unlabeled vowels. In this way, terminology like front of the tongue, back of the tongue, open, closed, labial, non-labial, explosive, slippery, etc. are used in both phonetics and phonology. If these concepts are phonetically connected to the fundamental characteristics of sounds, they are regarded in phonology as factors of distinction when phonemes are compared to one another. A phoneme is the smallest linguistic unit that distinguishes words, word forms, and morphemes—units that are superior to itself in the language. For instance, They can be distinguished thanks to the Uzbek language's "bir-bar-ber-bur-bor-bor" phonemes. For instance, the consonant phonemes in the words ben-ten-pen-men-red-bed-led serve to identify them in English. According to L.V. Sherba, words that show the opposition of one phoneme to another in such a specific location (such as "bur-bor" or "led-bed" in English) are referred to as quasihomonyms or words in minimal pairs. Typically, quasi-homonyms are used to estimate the number of phonemes in a language, and their distinctive characteristics are categorized by comparing one phoneme to another. For instance, two phonemes in the English words "tol-sol" and "tend (tent) -sent (send)" include explosive sliding differentiation parts (t | va | s). These indicators are referred to as indistinguishable elements since they are both obedient, voiceless, noisy consonants.

These defining characteristics aid in turning a certain particularity into commonality. Both the speaker and the audience remember commonalities. Therefore, despite the fact that this similarity is expressed differently, it has the same effect. Between the speaker and the listener, comprehension. A sound is defined as the smallest and most indivisible component of speech that is actually spoken during speech production and is audible to the ear. A phoneme is the smallest unit of language that can be directly observed and is responsible for forming and differentiating words and their semantic units, which are pronounced through a variety of sounds. Phonemes are not sequentially subdivided into other subdivisions.

To sum up, phonetics is a distinct independent discipline of linguistics that focuses on the study of the oral spoken sound system.

REFERENCES

1. Jalolov J. Methods of teaching foreign languages, "Teacher" Publishing House, Tashkent - 2012.
2. Jalilov S. Modern Uzbek literary language, Nukus, 2011.
3. <https://studfile.net/preview/7743829/page:2/>
4. Alfirovich M. T., Ogli S. K. S. COURAGE OF UZBEK PEOPLE IN THE BATTLE ON THE THRESHOLD OF STALINGRAD //Archive of Conferences. – 2021. – С. 100-103.
5. Мирзаев Т. А. Ватанпарварлик Туйғуси-Олий Фазилат //Conference Zone. – 2022. – С. 52-53.
6. Мирзаев Т. А. РАЗВИТИЕ КОММУНИКАТИВНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ У ОБУЧАЕМЫХ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ КАК ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2022. – №. 2 (71). – С. 78-80.
7. Mirzaev T. A., Shernazarov K. S. U. THE ROLE OF MILITARY EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AND THE MILITARY SPHERE //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 604-606.
8. Nizami M. T. A. et al. The Role of Military Education in Higher Educational Institutions and the Military Field //International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 5-6.